

AN OVERVIEW OF ARTESUNATE AND AMODIAQUINE HYDROCHLORIDE IN MALARIA TREATMENT

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ABSTRACT: Malaria remains a major global health concern, with *Plasmodium falciparum* and *Plasmodium vivax* being the most prevalent and deadly species. Artesunate and amodiaquine are widely used antimalarial drugs with distinct mechanisms of action and clinical applications. Artesunate, a water-soluble derivative of artemisinin, acts by generating reactive oxygen species that damage the malaria parasite, while amodiaquine, a 4-aminoquinoline, inhibits heme polymerization and disrupts parasite digestion. This review explores the pharmacokinetics, efficacy, safety profiles, and resistance patterns of these two drugs. Artesunate has proven to be highly effective in treating severe malaria and is recommended as part of combination therapy, particularly in cases of *P. falciparum* infection. Amodiaquine, although effective, has been associated with significant side effects, including hepatotoxicity and QT interval prolongation, limiting its use in certain populations. The combination of artesunate and amodiaquine has demonstrated synergistic effects, improving therapeutic outcomes while mitigating the risk of drug resistance. The review also discusses current challenges, including drug resistance, pharmacovigilance, and strategies for optimizing treatment regimens to enhance the global fight against malaria.

The development of fixed-dose combination (FDC) tablets for malaria treatment aims to improve therapeutic efficacy, reduce the risk of drug resistance, and enhance patient compliance. In this study, we explore the formulation of an inlay tablet containing the antimalarial drugs Artesunate and Amodiaquine. The inlay tablet design integrates both drugs into distinct layers to optimize their release profiles, allowing for controlled delivery and synergistic activity.

KEYWORDS: Malaria, Antimalarial drugs, Artesunate, Amodiaquine, *Plasmodium falciparum*, *Plasmodium vivax*.

INTRODUCTION-

Pharmaceutical tablets are defined as solid, flat or biconvex dishes that are made by compressing a medication or drug mixture, with or without diluents. This is in accordance with the Indian Pharmacopoeia. A tablet is a solid dosage form that has been compressed and contains medication, either with or without excipients.[3]

Among all the dosage forms that are currently accessible, tablets are the most commonly utilized due to their ease of administration, affordability, and elegance. Coating processes

determine aesthetic qualities like as colour, texture, mouthfeel, and taste masking. [1] Tablets can be chewed or swallowed whole. Before being administered, some are dissolved or distributed in water. A portion are placed in the mouth, where the active component releases at a set pace. Tablets can also be used to present passersines or implants. The shape, size, and weight of a tablet can vary significantly based on the medicinal substance's quantity and the intended manner of administration.[2]

Advantages of Tablet-

- 1) Comparing large-scale manufacturing to alternative dosage forms, it is possible. As a result, economic success is possible.
- 2) Because tablets are a solid unit dosage form, dosage accuracy is preserved. It is possible to have a customized release profile.
- 3) Strict environmental requirements are not necessary in the tablet section because tablets are not sterile dosage forms.
- 4) There are numerous tablet varieties to choose from, including chewable, effervescent, dispersible, floating, colon targeting, and buccal.
- 5) Simple handling and packaging (blister or strip) compared to liquid dosage forms
- 6) It is not necessary to have a physician or nurse present when administering parenteral. That is to say, self-management is feasible.
- 7) The greatest chemical and microbial stability are found in all oral dosage forms.
- 8) As a unit dosage form, tablets provide the most precise dose and least amount of content fluctuation of any oral dosage form.

Disadvantages of Tablet-

- 1) Difficult to swallow when a patient is unconscious or a children's.
- 2) Certain substances, like aspirin, have irritant effects on the GI mucosa.
- 3) It may be challenging to create or manufacture a tablet that will nevertheless give sufficient or complete drug bioavailability for medications with poor wetting, slow dissolving qualities, and optimal absorption high in the gastrointestinal tract.
- 4) There is relatively little liquid medication (like vitamin E or simethicone) that can be encased in a tablet.
- 5) A medicine with poor wettability and a sluggish rate of dissolution in a tablet is challenging to produce. [2,3]

TYPES OF TABLETS:

Oral Tablets for Ingestion-

- 1) Commonly Compressed Tablets
- 2) Multiple Tablets with Compression Coatings
 - a) Sugar Coated
 - b) Film Coated
 - c) Gelatine Coated
 - d) Enteric Coated
- 3) Layered Tablets
- 4) Targeted Tablets
 - a) Colon Targeting Tablets
 - b) Floating Tablets

- 5) Chewable Tablets
- 6) Dispersible Tablets
- 7) Inlay Tablets.

Tablets for the Dental Cavity-

- 1) Troches and Lozenges
- 2) Quick-Dissolving Tablets
- 3) Dental Cones
- 4) Sublingual Tablets
- 5) Buccal Tablets

Tablets Applied Through Different Channels

- 1) Vaginal Tablets
- 2) Rectal Tablets [3,4]

INLAY TABLETS-

An inlay tablet is a kind of multilayer tablet where the top surface is fully visible and the core tablet is totally encased in coating. With core rod tooling, tablet compression was achieved by incorporating the medicine into the cup section while leaving the other surface of the core exposed to the external environment. Just the bottom part of the die cavity is filled with coating material during preparation, and the core is then positioned on top of it. The entire tablet is compressed when portion of the coating material is displaced to form sides.

Granules without coating that are squeezed around the enteric-coated inlay section may make up the main body component. In order to provide time-delayed or sustained medication, the main body component of the tablet is first released and absorbed in the gastrointestinal tract, and the enteric coating shields the inlay portion of the tablet for a predetermined amount of time. [5,7]

One kind of stacked tablet is an inlay tablet. Only the bottom of the die chamber is filled with coating material during preparation, and the core is then positioned on top of it. A portion of the coating material is moved to form the sides and compress the entire tablet when compression force is applied. It is a cutting-edge platform technology that reduces mechanical shear on double-compressed products, perhaps reducing unidentified contaminants linked to the process. This dose form can also be used to develop incompatible medications. [7]

Advantages of inlay tablets-

- 1) It is possible to produce a dosage form with both an immediate-release and a sustained-release active component.
- 2) Highly soluble medications frequently have the burst effect, which is a significant release over a brief period of time. This should be avoided as it could result in a high concentration of the active ingredients in the bloodstream.
- 3) The plasma level can be kept steady and within the therapeutic range for the duration of the course of treatment.
- 4) Possesses the capacity to release medications, both soluble and insoluble, in dissolving fluids at a zero-order rate of release. Highly water-soluble medication dosages can be lowered while maintaining the same level of efficacy.
- 5) It is possible to prevent side effects from subtherapeutic plasma concentrations.

- 6) It is possible to produce tablets in a variety of shapes, including triangle, rectangular, and capsule forms.[6]

MALARIA: -

Malaria is named after the Italian word "malaria," which translates to "bad air," to symbolize the disease's connection to swampy regions. One In tropical and subtropical areas across the world, protozoan parasites of the genus Plasmodium are the cause of this endemic vector-borne parasitic disease. More than 200 species of Plasmodium infect mammals, birds, and reptiles, and malaria parasites are often host-specific. The parasites have a complicated life cycle that involves both vertebrate hosts and a mosquito vector. Additionally, it reproduces asexually as well as sexually. This makes it difficult to design medications and vaccines.

Plasmodium falciparum is the most virulent of the Plasmodium species that cause malaria, accounting for the majority of the disease's morbidity and fatality rates globally (Peter and Anatoli 1998). Other human-infecting Plasmodium species include, P. ovale, P. knowlesi, P. malaria, and P. vivax. The World Health Organization (2019) estimates that there were 228 million cases of malaria worldwide in 2018. [9,11]

Throughout the mosquito-human life cycle, the six human malaria parasite species— Plasmodium falciparum, Plasmodium vivax, Plasmodium ovalewallickeri, Plasmodium ovalecurtisi, Plasmodium malaria, and Plasmodium knowlesi—go through ten or more morphological states, replicate from one to 10,000 β cells, and vary in population size from one to many more than 10^6 organisms. Only a tiny percentage of these morphological phases result in clinical illness in the human host, and the majority of malaria patients worldwide exhibit minimal, if any, symptoms.[10]

Epidemiology of Malaria-

With the amazing success of the DDT and chloroquine discoveries after World War II, the global ranges of *P. vivax* and *P. falciparum* were reduced, and vast regions of the Americas, Europe, and Asia benefited. Until the first decade of the twenty-first century, these amazing advancements in malaria control persisted; however, the second decade seems to be a little more difficult. Since 2014, the prevalence of malaria has increased in a number of locations. An estimated 229 million cases were recorded globally in 2019 (from 87 countries where malaria is endemic). Approximately 94% of the 215 million cases that were documented occurred in Africa. Approximately 3% of all malaria cases worldwide occurred in Southeast Asia. An estimated 409,000 people died from malaria globally that year, with 94% of those deaths occurring in Africa.

Etiology of Malaria-

Photosynthetic protozoa called Dinoflagellates are the source of Plasmodium parasites. At least 13 of the approximately 200 protozoan species that have been identified thus far are known to be harmful to humans. Human malaria is known to be caused by five parasites: *P. falciparum*, *P. vivax*, *P. malariae*, *P. ovale* (including *P. ovalecurtisi* and *P. ovalewallikeri*), and *P. knowlesi*. *P. falciparum* is the most common and harmful species in Africa. Nonetheless, the majority of malaria-endemic places in Africa exhibit co-infection and the presence of many sympatric species in a single human host or mosquito vector.[11,12]

DRUG PROFILE-**1. ARTESUNATE**

Attribute	Details
Structure.	
Drug Name	Artesunate
Molecular Weight	384.43 g/mol
Molecular Formula	C ₁₉ H ₂₈ O ₈
Molecular Structure	(Image not provided)
Chemical Name	(3R,5aS,6R,8aS,9R,10S,12R,12aR)- Decahydro-3,6,9-trimethyl-3,12-epoxy- 12H-pyrano[4,3-j]- 1,2-benzodioxepin- 10-ol, hydrogen succinate
Appearance	White crystalline powder
Solubility	Soluble in Ethyl acetate
Melting Point	138-140°C
Class	Artemisinin
Half-life	0.22-0.30 hours
Therapeutic Use	The first-line treatment for severe malaria in adults or children artesunate. [13,14,15]

2. AMODIAQUINE HYDROCHLORIDE

Attribute	Details
Structure.	 V
Drug Name	Amodiaquine hydrochloride
Molecular Weight	325.83 g/mol

Molecular Formula	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ Cl ₃ N ₃ O
Molecular Structure	(Image not provided)
Chemical Name	4-[(7-chloroquinolin-4-yl) amino]-2-(diethylaminomethyl) phenol; dihydrochloride
Appearance	A yellow crystalline powder
Solubility	Soluble in water, sparingly soluble in ethanol
Melting Point	160–165°C
Class	4-aminoquinoline
Half-life	5.3-7.7 hours
Therapeutic Use	Used in the treatment of malaria, especially as part of combination therapy

MARKETED FORMULATIONS OF ARTESUNATE AND AMODIAQUINE:

- 1) Camoquin- Amodiaquine and artesunate are used together to treat simple malaria.
- 2) Coarsucam- A mix of amodiaquine and artesunate.

MATERIALS AND METHOD-

Ingredients-

- Binders: - Eg- Povidone, Starch, Stearic acid, Hydroxyl propyl methyl cellulose, poly vinyl pyrrolidine, Lactose, etc
- Lubricant: - Eg- Magnesium stearate, Stearic acid, Polyethylene glycols, etc
- Glidant: - Eg- Talc, Magnesium carbonate, calcium carbonate, Silica derivatives, etc
- Diluents: -Eg- Microcrystalline cellulose, lactose, mannitol, Hypromellose, calcium phosphate, calcium sulphate, etc[17]

Method of Preparation-

Preparation Of Inlay Tablet-

The three steps are as follows:

1. Preparation of core tablet
2. Preparation of cup portion
3. Preparation of inlay tablet [2,1]

1. Material Selection

- **Active Ingredient:** Choose the drug to be incorporated.
- **Excipients:** Select suitable excipients for the core and the coating layer, including binders, fillers, disintegrants, and lubricants

2. Preparation of Core

- **Mixing:** Blend the active ingredient with excipients (fillers, binders, etc.) to achieve a uniform mixture.
- **Granulation:** If needed, perform wet or dry granulation to enhance flow and compaction properties.
- **Compression:** Compress the granulated material into tablets using a tablet press.

3. Preparation of Inlay Coating

- **Coating Solution:** Prepare a coating solution that may include polymers (e.g., hydroxypropyl methylcellulose) for controlled release, colorants, or flavoring agents.
- **Application:** Apply the coating to the core tablets using methods like pan coating, fluidized bed coating, or spray coating.

4. Drying

- Ensure that the coated tablets are dried adequately to remove solvents and maintain stability.

5. Final Compression (if necessary)

- Optionally, a second compression step may be performed to improve tablet integrity and hardness. [2,6,17]

EVALUATION OF GRANULES:

Granules are crucial ingredient in the creation of numerous solid dosage forms, including tablets and capsules, are granules. To guarantee the end product's efficacy, uniformity, and quality, their assessment is essential. A number of tests and evaluations are used to analyze the mechanical, chemical, and physical characteristics of granules. The objective is to guarantee that the granules fulfill the necessary requirements for stability, homogeneity, and drug delivery.

The following standard metrics and tests are used to assess granules:

1. Size and Size Distribution-

The consistency of the powder blend, flow characteristics, and content uniformity are all influenced by granule size. The drug's bioavailability and rate of dissolution are also impacted by the size distribution.

- **Methods:**

- **Sieve Analysis:** Granules are passed through a series of sieves to determine the percentage of granules in each size range.
- **Laser Diffraction:** Uses light scattering to measure the granule size distribution. [18,19]

2. Moisture Content-

Granules stability, flowability, and compressibility are all impacted by their moisture level. While too little moisture might cause brittle granules, too much moisture can cause microbial development or deterioration.

Methods:

Loss on Drying (LOD): The granules are heated to remove moisture, and the weight loss is measured.

3. Measurements of Flow-

MgSt-B, MgSt-V, and MgSt-F grades and powder blends were used to test flow characteristics. Because it influences how easily the granules may be handled, combined, and processed into tablets or capsules, their flowability is a crucial characteristic in pharmaceutical formulations. Problems like uneven tablet weight, irregular content consistency, or processing delays might arise from poor flowability.

Granule flowability can be measured using a variety of standard methodologies and techniques, some of which can be evaluated visually or using simple tools. The most popular techniques for determining flowability are listed below:

A] Angle of Repose:

The angle created by the edge of a cone-shaped pile of granules and the horizontal base of the bench surface is known as the angle of repose. The employed funnel was made of stainless steel, with an opening that measured 10 mm in diameter, and was 111 mm high from start to finish. Four centimetres above the bench surface, the funnel was secured in position. Following the construction of the cone from 5 g of material, measurements were made of the radius (r) of the base and the height (h) of the grains composing the cone. The following formula was used to determine the angle of repose (θ):

Formula's $\theta = \tan^{-1} h/r$

where:

- h = height of the pile,
- r = radius of the base of the pile.

Sr. No.	Flowability	Angle Of Repose
1	Excellent	<25
2	Good	25-30
3	Moderate Flow	30-40
4	Poor Flow	>40

B] Bulk density:

A measurement used to characterize a particle packing is called bulk density. It was calculated using a measuring cylinder and balance, and it is (gm/ml).¹⁹ At first, the measuring cylinder's weight was tarred. Next, a funnel was used to pour 4 grams of presieved (40) bulk medication into the measurement cylinder. The powder's volume was then measured. Using the following formula, the granules' bulk density was determined.

Formula: Bulk density = Weight of powder / Volume of powder [23]

C] Tapped density:

A graduated cylinder filled with the same mass of powder used for B.D. is placed on a mechanical tapper device and run for a predetermined number of taps (about 500) until the powder bed volume reaches a minimum in order to calculate the taped density.

Formula: Tapped density = Weight of powder / min. *volume of powder

D] Compressibility Index (Carr’s Index):

A powder's propensity to consolidate, or join to form a solid form, is gauged by its compressibility index (CI). As such it is a measure of inter-particulate interactions. In a free-flowing powder, inter-particulate interactions are generally less significant, and the bulk and tapped densities will be closer in value. For poorer flowing materials, there are frequently greater inter-particle interactions; bridging between particles often result in lower bulk density and a greater difference between the bulk and tapped densities. The CI reflects these variations in particle interactions. It is crucial for preserving consistent tablet weight and the best possible flowability of powders. Better flow is indicated by a lower compressibility rating.

Formula:

$$\text{Carr's index (\%)} = \frac{[(\text{Tapped density} - \text{bulk density})/\text{tapped density}] * 100}$$

E] Hausner’s ratio (HR):

In powder technology, Hausner's Ratio is a metric used to evaluate a powder's flowability. It is stated by Hausner. A material's Hausner ratio value might change based on the methods employed to calculate it, hence it is not an absolute attribute. However, because the tools needed to do the analysis are reasonably priced and the method is simple to learn, the usage of these metrics continues.

Formula:

$$\text{Hausner's ratio} = \text{Tapped density} / \text{Bulk density} [20,21,22]$$

Sr. No.	Flowability	Carr’s Index (%)	Hausner’s Ratio
1	Excellent	0-10	1.00-1.11
2	Good	10-15	1.12-1.18
3	Fair	16-20	1.19-1.25
4	Possible	21-25	1.26-1.34
5	Poor	26-31	1.35-1.34

EVALUATION OF TABLETS:

A crucial step in the production of pharmaceuticals is the evaluation of tablets to make sure they fulfill strict requirements for safety, effectiveness, and quality. Numerous physical and chemical characteristics are included in this assessment, as they are crucial for both regulatory compliance and consumer acceptance.

A] Colour and Appearance-

The colour and look of the compressed tablets were assessed.

B] Tablet thickness-

Using a vernier calliper, the thickness of ten randomly chosen tablets from the prepared tablets was measured; the mean of these readings was used to calculate the mean tablet thickness.

C] Weight variation test-

Twenty pills were selected from each batch for this purpose, and each was weighed separately using an analytical balance. Using a computer-based Excel application, the mean and standard deviation were determined, and the results were documented appropriately. [24,25]

D] Hardness-

This relates to the strength of the tablet and is determined by tools like the Pfizer or Monsanto testers. Usually, a hardness of 5 to 8 kg/cm² is considered adequate. Tablets that pass hardness testing are guaranteed to be resistant to mechanical shocks during handling and transportation. The mean crushing strength was determined using ten pills.

E] Friability-

This evaluates how resistant the tablet is to breaking and chipping. For this test, which often uses a Roche friabilator, tablets that lose less than 0.5% to 1% of their weight are deemed acceptable.

The friability (F) is given by the formula:

$$F = (1 - W_o/W) \times 100$$

F] Content Uniformity-

This test makes sure that, within predetermined bounds (85% to 115% of the listed content), each tablet contains the right amount of active component. Tablets are randomly sampled to ensure adherence to these guidelines.

G] Dissolution test-

Under controlled circumstances, the rate at which an active ingredient releases from a solid dosage form is measured via dissolution testing. The effectiveness of tablets, capsules, films, and other solids is evaluated using this method. In order to guide the formulation development process and compare final products with other commercial preparations, dissolution testing is helpful. Dissolution testing can also be used to evaluate a sample's quality by figuring out whether the formulation's active medicinal component release falls within allowable bounds.

E] Disintegration test-

The disintegration test calculates how long it will take for a batch of pills to break up into particles that can fit through a 10-mesh screen under specific circumstances. After oral administration, a medication must first be in solution in order to be absorbed from a solid dosage form. Disintegration, or the breaking up of the tablet, is typically the first crucial step toward this condition. Based on the circumstances, the IP has defined the range for the disintegration of various tablet kinds. [26,27,28,29]

CYTOTOXICITY STUDY OF DRUG

Cytotoxicity tests were performed on two antimalarial drugs: Artesunate (ART) Amodiaquine. Stock solutions (10,000 µg/mL) were prepared in 10% DMSO, and test solutions (31.3–1,000 µg/mL) were diluted in RPMI-1640 medium. DMSO served as a positive control.

The cytotoxic effects were assessed using three tumor-derived cell lines (HepG2, HeLa S3, TOV-21G) and two non-tumor cell lines (BGMK, WI-26VA4). Cells were cultured in RPMI 1640 medium with 10% FBS and maintained at 37°C with 5% CO₂.

Human monocytes were isolated from donor blood using a Monopaque density gradient and centrifugation. The monocyte layer was collected, washed with PBS, and resuspended to a final concentration of 1×10^6 cells in 180 μ L. The study aimed to evaluate the cytotoxic impact of antimalarial drugs on different cell types.[36]

DRUG RELEASE KINETICS:

Drug release kinetics, which establish the rate and process by which the active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) is released into the body, are essential to the efficacy of pharmaceutical tablets. Designing controlled or modified-release formulations, guaranteeing consistent therapeutic effects, and maximizing medication bioavailability all depend on the knowledge of drug release kinetics. The mathematical modeling and analysis of a drug's rate of release from a dosage form is known as drug release kinetics. Predicting in vivo drug performance and customizing drug formulations to attain intended therapeutic results require an understanding of these dynamics.

A) Zero-Order Kinetics-

Regardless of drug concentration, the rate of drug release remains constant.

The formula makes the assumption that time and cumulative drug release are directly correlated. The equation may be as follows:

$$C = K_0 t \text{-----} (1)$$

where t is the time in hours and K_0 is the zero order rate constant expressed in units of concentration/time. A concentration vs. time graph would show a straight line with a slope of K_0 that intercepts the axes' origin.

B) First order equation-

The log cumulative proportion of medication remaining vs. time represents the release behavior of the first order equation. The equation may be as follows:

$$\text{Log } C = \text{Log } C_0 - kt / 2.303 \text{-----} (2)$$

Where, C = The amount of drug un-dissolved at t time,

C_0 = Drug concentration at $t = 0$,

k = Corresponding release rate constant.

C) Higuchi square root law-

The cumulative percentage of drug release versus the square root of time is described by the Higuchi release model. The equation may be as follows:

$$Q = K\sqrt{t} \text{-----} (3)$$

where K is the constant that represents the system's design factors and Q is the amount of medication dissolved at time t . The reciprocal of the square root of time is therefore proportional to the medication release rate.[30,31,32]

D) Hixson-Crowell cube root law-

It is the law that illustrates how the surface area and diameter of the particles or tablets affect the assessment of drug release patterns. It is expressed as the cube root of the drug retention percentage in the matrix as a function of time. The equation may be as follows:

$$Q_0^{1/3} - Q_t^{1/3} = k_{HC} \times t \text{-----} (4)$$

Where, Q_0 = Initial amount of the drug in the tablets.

Q_t = The amount of drug release in time 't'.

k_{HC} = The rate constant for the Hixson-Crowell cube root law.

E) Korsmeyer–Peppas equation-

A straightforward, semi-empirical model that exponentially relates the drug release to the elapsed time was created by Korsmeyer et al. The equation may be as follows:

$$Q/Q_0 = K t^n \text{-----} (5)$$

Where, Q/Q_0 = The fraction of drug released at time 't'.

k = Constant comprising the structural geometric characteristics.

n = The diffusion exponent that depends on the release mechanism.[30,31,32]

STABILITY STUDIES:

Drug substances and products are routinely subjected to stability testing, which is used at different phases of product development. Accelerated stability testing (at comparatively high temperatures and/or humidity) is done in the early phases to identify the kinds of degradation products that might be discovered after extended storage. In order to guarantee that tablets retain their quality, safety, and effectiveness throughout their shelf life, stability studies are crucial in the pharmaceutical development process. By assessing physical, chemical, microbiological, and medicinal stability, these investigations assist in determining the best packing, storage conditions, and expiration dates.[33,34]

Real-Time stability testing- In order to account for substantial product degradation under suggested storage circumstances, real-time stability testing is typically conducted for a longer test period. The test's duration is determined by the product's stability; it must be sufficient to make it evident that no detectable degradation is taking place and to allow one to differentiate between degradation and inter-assay variance. Data is gathered at a suitable rate during the testing process so that a trend analysis can differentiate between instability and daily ambiguity.

Accelerated stability testing- A product is stressed at a number of high (warmer than ambient) temperatures during accelerated stability testing in order to calculate the amount of heat input necessary to trigger product breakdown. This is done in order to expose the product to conditions that hasten its degradation. After that, this data is projected to forecast shelf life or to evaluate the relative stability of different formulations. This typically shortens the development schedule by giving an early indication of the product's shelf life. During accelerated stability testing, stress factors such as moisture, light, agitation, gravity, pH, and packing are used in addition to temperature.[35]

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